

Faculty of Medicine
Department of Community Medicine
International University of Africa
Batch 21

**ABSENTEEISM AMONG UNDERGRADUATE
MEDICAL STUDENTS AT THE INTERNATIONAL
UNIVERSITY OF AFRICA-2022**

Prepared by:

Janneh Muhammed Lamin

Oumar Hamit Khamis

Ramla Abdinasir Omar

Sarah Madyan Saeed Salem

Tasneem Gadalla Elhag Adlan

Proposal submitted in partial fulfilment of the academic requirements of the
Degree of MBBS

Supervisor: **Dr. Asim Abdelmoneim Hussein**

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to our parents, and then everyone who has ever taught us beneficial knowledge, especially the medical staff of the International University of Africa.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our supervisor for this project, Dr. Asim Abdelmoneim Hussein, for the countless hours he spent reading, reviewing and reflecting on our thesis. We are equally thankful for his encouragement and support throughout this research process. Without his guidance and feedback, this research would not be complete.

Our sincere thanks also goes to all those who volunteered to participate in this study.

Finally, we would like to thank the entire faculty and staff of the Medical School of the International University of Africa whose support was crucial to our professional development.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

I.U.A: International University of Africa

WHO: World Health Organization

MD: Doctor of Medicine

MBBS: Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery

GPA: Grade Point Average

KSAU-HS: King Saud Bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences

SPSS: Statistical Package of Social Sciences

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title	Page No.
Dedication	I
Acknowledgments	II
List of Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	III
Table of Contents	IV
List of Tables	V
List of Figures	V
Abstract (English Version)	VI
Abstract (Arabic Version)	VII
Chapter One: Introduction:	1 – 3
▪ 1.1 Background.....	1
▪ 1.2 Problem Statement	2
▪ 1.3 Rationale	2
▪ 1.4 Research Objectives.....	3
Chapter Two: Literature Review:	4 - 7
Chapter Three: Materials and Methods:	8 – 10
▪ 3.1 Study Design	8
▪ 3.2 Study Area	8
▪ 3.3 Study Duration	8
▪ 3.4 Study Population.....	8
▪ 3.5 Variables	9
▪ 3.6 Sampling.....	9
▪ 3.7 Data Collection.....	10
▪ 3.8 Data Analysis.....	10
▪ 2.9 Ethical Considerations.....	10
Chapter Four: Results	11 – 18
Chapter Five: Discussion and Conclusion	19 – 22
Chapter Six: Recommendations and Limitations	23 – 24
References	25
Annex 1: The Questionnaire	28
Annex 2: Budget Estimation	31
Annex 3: Timetable.....	31
Annex 4: Maps	32

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Table Title	Page No.
Table (4.1)	Distribution of participants according to Age, Gender, Marital Status, Nationality, Reasons for Studying Medicine etc. Faculty of Medicine, I.U.A. Khartoum, Sudan. (n=110)	
Table (4.2)	Participants' Response on the Reasons for not attending Lectures. Faculty of Medicine, I.U.A. Khartoum, Sudan. (n=110)	

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Figure Title	Page No.
Figure (4.1)	Participants' responses according to time taken to reach the faculty/college. Medical School, I.U.A. (n=110)	
Figure (4.2)	Participants' Dependence on YouTube. I.U.A. Medical School. (n=110)	
Figure (4.3)	Participants' Dependence on Medical Apps for Knowledge. I.U.A. Medical School. (n=110)	
Figure (4.4)	Participants' responses on feelings of homesickness. I.U.A. Medical School. (=110)	

ABSTRACT

Background: Student absenteeism is widespread. Many factors have been implicated as potential causes of this phenomenon, ranging from academic, social, psychological and personal.

Objectives: The aim of this study is to examine the reasons for medical student absenteeism at the International University of Africa, and to assess whether new technology such as YouTube and medical apps contribute to the matter.

Materials & Methods: This was a descriptive, cross-sectional and institution-based study, with a sample size of 110 medical students in their 4th and 5th academic years. A random sampling technique was used to collect data within a month. Participants were asked to fill a well-structured and confidential questionnaire with ethical clearance obtained from each of them.

Results: The results have shown that the causes of medical student absenteeism are multifactorial. Yet strikingly, dependence on alternative sources of medical information such as those provided by YouTube and medical apps has increasingly become a dominant factor.

Conclusion: Absenteeism is gradually becoming more prevalent and medical school administrations, faculty members as well as the students should collectively devise effective means to synergistically confront it. Such approach is necessary because the topic in question is widely reported as a potential reason for low academic performance.

مستخلص البحث

الخلفية: لقد انتشر التغيب عن المحاضرات بين الطلاب. وتم التورط في هذه الظاهرة العديد من العوامل التي تتراوح من الأكاديمية والاجتماعية والنفسية والشخصية.

الأهداف: الهدف من هذه الدراسة هو فحص أسباب تغيب طلاب الطب في جامعة إفريقيا العالمية عن المحاضرات، وتقييم ما إذا كانت التكنولوجيا الجديدة مثل يوتوب والتطبيقات الطبية تساهم في هذه المسألة.

المواد والطرق: كانت هذه دراسة وصفية ومقطعية وقائمة على المؤسسة، مع حجم عينة يحتوي ١١٠ من طلاب الطب في العامين الأكاديميين الرابع والخامس. تم استخدام تقنية أخذ العينات العشوائية لجمع البيانات في غضون شهر. طُلب من المشاركين ملء استبيان منظم جيداً وسرياً مع الموافقة الأخلاقية التي تم الحصول عليها من كل منهم.

النتائج: أظهرت النتائج أن أسباب تغيب طلاب الطب عن الدروس متعددة العوامل. ومع ذلك، من اللافت للنظر أن الاعتماد على مصادر بديلة للمعلومات الطبية مثل تلك التي يوفرها يوتوب والتطبيقات الطبية أصبح عاملاً مهيمناً بشكل متزايد.

الخلاصة: أصبح الغياب أكثر انتشاراً بشكل تدريجي ويجب على إدارات كليات الطب وأعضاء هيئة التدريس والطلاب أن يبتكروا بشكل جماعي وسائل فعالة لمواجهة بشكل تآزري. هذا النهج ضروري لأن الموضوع المعني يتم الإبلاغ عنه على نطاق واسع كسبب محتمل للأداء الأكاديمي المنخفض.

CHAPTER ONE

1. Introduction

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Student absenteeism is a prevalent phenomenon in many tertiary educational institutions⁽¹⁾. As the world has become more digitalized, accessory sources of information comes to mind as a potential cause. Yet any broad conjecture on this matter without factoring the specific conditions of different universities and their students reserves a tendency to be biased. Apparently, no single explanation is sufficient to describe the behaviors and tastes of varying groups of people. The Medical School of the International University of Africa (IUA) puts a lot of emphasis on attendance, yet this effort has fallen short of totally resolving the absenteeism problem among students.

Absenteeism is widely believed to be an indicator of low level of motivation for learning⁽²⁾. There is extensive literature on the link between absenteeism and lack of subject matter interest, poor teaching strategies, unfavorable learning environment, transport problems, inconvenient lecture times, peer influence, part-time jobs, ill health, sleeplessness and poor relations with lecturers⁽³⁾. In addition, as alluded above, accessibility of lecture contents in the form of online slides, videos and audios hold a notable proportion of contribution to this problem⁽⁴⁾.

Regular attendance of lectures is significant for the students' educational achievements, professional and social change. Students who attend classes regularly can be successful in their future professional lives through completing work-related skills such as determination, problem-solving and the ability to work with others synergistically. Regular students are deemed to have better job opportunities⁽⁵⁾. Students who don't attend classes regularly have lower academic performance, limited future employment opportunities and they often experience social and emotional complications⁽⁶⁾. Absenteeism not only affects the academic advancement of the student, but also influences the in-class planning of teachers as well as the enthusiasm of other students in the class. Chronic absenteeism has a significant relationship with dangerous behaviors such as substance abuse, violence, physical injury and eventual dropout⁽⁷⁾.

Lectures remain one of the essential methods of teaching in many medical colleges regardless of adaptation of new curriculum.^(8,9) With the increase use of electronic equipment, there is a variety

of software inputs developed to assist in making lectures more presentable, interesting and interactive—hence making the learning process more effective. One would expect this advancement to curb the problem of absenteeism but that is not the case. In fact, not all schools have acquired such new teaching technology. After all, absenteeism at higher education level affects the learning process of the students as well as their final results at the end of the academic session.⁽¹⁰⁾

1.2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Student academic performance has been identified by previous researchers as directly linked to their attendance of lectures. So apparently, lecture attendance is indispensable, and students can simultaneously make use of other sources of learning to expand their knowledge. This is the ideal situation. Yet many students increasingly prefer the use of accessory sources of information most notably YouTube, a platform which provides them access to loads of medical information and clinical skills. This study will seek to find out how effective YouTube is as a learning platform and also assess the level of student dependence on it as well as their impetus for doing so. This will help Medical Schools to know why students forgo lectures for YouTube and assist them in determining what programs they can initiate to reverse this phenomenon, for if the problem of absenteeism is not solved, students will continue to underperform academically. The study will also focus on the impact of medical apps on this matter.

1.3. RATIONALE

There is insufficient research into the impact of YouTube on student absenteeism, a phenomenon which has become rampant among medical students across the globe. This study aims to close that gap.

1.4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

General Objective:

To assess the factors that contribute to absenteeism among undergraduate medical students at the International University of Africa (I.U.A)

Specific Objectives:

- To explore the perceptions of students regarding absenteeism
- To assess students' knowledge on the impacts of absenteeism
- To measure students' dependence on YouTube
- To determine if language barrier causes student absenteeism
- To assess when absenteeism is more common—early or late years of medical school

CHAPTER TWO

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

Student absenteeism refers to the frequent absence from classes without any good reason. It is thought to be a primary concern in health profession education worldwide mainly in medical schools ⁽¹¹⁾. Absenteeism behavior may negatively affect the general educational process and personal academic achievements of students. The teaching and learning environment will be affected as it may form an unwelcoming and dull learning environment for both lecturers and students. Attendance is essential in the academic performance and professional development of medical students ⁽¹²⁾. The completion of the total credit hours in the aspect of academic and clinical contact is necessary to gain competence and ability to obtain Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS). Lectures, laboratory, and clinical sessions provide an invaluable learning experience and in-depth information that are crucial for medical students' academic success. Lecturers offer a personal, professional experience that accentuate the factual knowledge provided in each learning session which cannot simply be provided via textbooks ⁽¹³⁾.

2.2. Significance of Attendance

Also, student-lecturer interaction during a lecture or clinical session may provide priceless information and specific examples that make learning a subject more intuitive. Therefore, absentees are subject to miss these rich educational resources. This loss may negatively impact student academic performance.

In spite of compulsory attendance rule, every student's parents, institute, and society suffer when students do not attend classes in medical college on a regular basis. Poor execution of lecturing among teachers, ineffective teaching strategies and availability of learning resources on the internet were cited as some of the most common reasons of student absenteeism in medical schools ⁽¹⁴⁾. Also, studying while working has a considerable reason for the absences of students. Other factors such as sleeplessness, poor health status, busy social life and stress due to overload in learning tasks and assignments were reported to have caused absenteeism among students in medical and other health sciences related higher education ⁽¹⁵⁾.

2.3. Previous Studies

The relationship between absenteeism and course performance has been investigated in several studies. In such, studies conducted in several universities in South Africa, Saudi Arabia, as well in the United States revealed that students' absenteeism and academic performance has a negative correlation. Thus, it implies that the probability of students to obtain a high grade is in part dependent on maintaining a good attendance ⁽¹⁶⁾.

A meta-analysis consisting 52 published articles and 16 unpublished papers on the impact of absenteeism on students' academic performance found a negative association. ⁽¹⁷⁾

In a cross sectional study design conducted in 152 medical students of King Saud Bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences (KSAU-HS), Saudi Arabia; a total of 143 (92.76%) participated in the study, 72 % of whom were male and 28% were female. They have a mean age of 22.5 (± 2.02) and a mean GPA of 4.4 (± 0.4). 53.8% of the students were absent for 5 times or more in lectures/basic and clinical sciences sessions plus clinical diagnostic sessions. These absences are mainly a result of intense studying (n=36, 25.2%) and course dissatisfaction (n=32, 22.4%). However, only 3 (2.1%) had an absence for 5 times or more in Problem Based Learning (PBL) sessions, and they were mainly because of sleep (n=11, 7.7%) and family commitments (n=10, 7.0%). There is an inverse correlation between absenteeism and academic performance, this their conclusion was that absenteeism does have a negative impact on the academic performance of medical students. ⁽¹⁸⁾

The question inevitably arises: does non-attendance, in fact, affect students' success in a course? The answer according to Longhurst ⁽¹⁹⁾ is "yes", although it is generally recognized that not all students learn best from a 'lecture-type' scenario. There seems to be some concern moreover that non-attendance is indicative of lower levels of motivation amongst students. The importance of the issue can be seen in reports and articles such as that presented by Longhurst ⁽¹⁹⁾ who noted that "figures of the order of one quarter of all students absent on any given day are not unusual". Longhurst noted that absenteeism resulted in poor learning for those absent.

2.4. Reasons for Non-attendance

Absence can be viewed as a very personal decision based on both the ability to attend and the motivation to attend. The individual decision to come to lectures will be influenced by many factors. At one extreme, there will be those conditions which make attendance virtually impossible, while at the other extreme there are circumstances where managers or lecturers would say that there is no justification whatsoever for non-attendance. A large number of students are not able to attend due to employment commitments. Two-fifths of students in the UK claim that their university education is suffering because they have to work part-time. Half of the students interviewed in a survey of 782 third-year undergraduates for the National Institute of Economic and Social Research had to work while studying at university. Four-fifths of these said it meant they miss out on lectures and on using library and computer facilities. Ford et al ⁽²⁰⁾ also studied the impact of casual work on students' academic performance, and noted that various surveys had shown the large number – between about 27% and 57% - of students taking up some form of part-time work. This seemingly caused absence. Longhurst ⁽¹⁹⁾, on the other hand identified that in a study of FE college students "22% had missed classes at some time because of work commitments", but added that those with jobs "were no more likely to have been absent than those without jobs".

Although work may be affecting student attendance at lectures, there are some more fundamental reasons as to why students choose not to turn up for lectures. A study at Lincoln University in 1992 ⁽²¹⁾ found that the major reasons given by students for non-attendance at lectures were competing assessment pressures (24% of reasons given), poor lecturing (23%), timing of the lecture (16%) and poor quality of the lecture content (9%). Students, Fleming surmised, choose to miss a class in order to work on an assignment because they think they will gain more (marks) from doing the assignment. A 1995 replicating study at Lincoln University found that 40% of the reasons offered for non-attendance at lectures involved "the pressure of other learning tasks". No comment was made on the absence of any significant reference to poor lecturing and/or lecture content compared to the earlier survey.

2.5. The Problem of Poor Motivation

Motivation as a construct is an important issue in relation to the study of absence. It has been extensively studied both in the organization behavior and in the educational literature. There is, for example, a distinct difference between the motivation of those who want to learn, and those who have to learn. Race, for instance, states that “wanting to learn is the most satisfactory state for students to be in”.

Human learning is allegedly motivated by a combination of two kinds of rewards: extrinsic and intrinsic. Learning is extrinsically motivated when the anticipated rewards come from outside the activity. In a university setting extrinsic motivation can be sparked off by a drive to get good grades or wanting to win a prize for a given task. A person learns for the sake of intrinsic rewards when the performance itself is worth doing for its own sake, even in the absence of external rewards. Most learning in schools is extrinsically motivated. Arguably, the acquisition of knowledge is rarely enjoyed for its own sake, and relatively few young people would continue to learn in schools in the absence of parental and social pressure. Students who are intrinsically motivated tend to have higher achievement scores ⁽²²⁾. Factors influencing intrinsic motivation include students’ interest in the subject, an overall wish to succeed, a desire to prove themselves, their attitude towards the tutor, the satisfaction they gain from resource materials, and the amount of tutor encouragement present. It is not known whether extrinsically rather than intrinsically motivated students are more likely to attend lectures, but one of the aims of this study is to investigate this matter.

Writing from an educational perspective, Entwistle ⁽²³⁾ noted that staff did not always see it as their responsibility to motivate students. In looking at students’ motivational levels (be it extrinsic or intrinsic), he found that, according to student comments, part of the reason for downward movements in motivation and nonattendance were the staff themselves. Indeed, Bennett ⁽²⁴⁾ argued that lecturers with poor opinions of contemporary students, lecturers with low levels of regard for their students’ motivation, competence and behavior might not feel as committed to their teaching duties as others. Also, Bennett noted, such lecturers might adopt teaching methods and technologies different to those employed by lecturers who hold their students in high regard.

CHAPTER THREE

3. Materials And Methods

3.1. Study Design

This study was a descriptive, cross-sectional institution-based study. The reason for the use of this method is to accurately assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices of students regarding absenteeism and presenting the data in a comprehensive, meaningful way which allows for simple interpretations.

3.2. Study area

The study was conducted at the Medical Faculty of the International University of Africa (I.U.A). It is a private university in Khartoum, Sudan, and it is a member of the Federation of Universities of the Islamic World. The IUA Medical School aims to produce responsible and ethical medical doctors committed to life-long learning as it seeks to improve health indicators in Africa and the world at large. It awards a Bachelors of Medicine and Surgery after five years of studies, with English and Arabic as the languages of instruction.

3.3. Study Duration

The study was conducted from August 23rd, 2022 to November 1st, 2022.

3.4. Study Population

Medical students at the International University of Africa

Inclusion Criteria:

4th year to 5th year medical students at the International University of Africa.

Exclusion Criteria:

All other non-medical students of the International University of Africa.

Students from outside the University.

Medical students of the University unwilling to participate in the study.

3.5. Variables

Dependent Variables:

Knowledge, experience, attitudes and habits of the medical students with respect to absenteeism.

Independent Variables:

Reasons for studying Medicine, mode of transportation, time taken to reach college, place of having meals, meal time coinciding with lectures etc.

Background Variables:

Age, gender, marital status, nationality.

3.6. Sampling

Sample Size

n=110

Sampling Technique

A random sampling method was used to collect the sample.

3.7. Data Collection

Technique:

Data was collected by means of a simple questionnaire written in simple English.

Tools:

Electronic, administrated, structured, close-ended questionnaires were used.

3.8. Data Analysis

The data collected was analysed through simple random sampling calculation. Initially, all information gathered via questionnaire was coded into variables.

3.9. Ethical Considerations

Permission was taken from both the Research Committee and the Dean's office at the Faculty of Medicine of the International University of Africa. The purpose of the study was explained to students in detail before administering questionnaires and only participants voluntarily willing to take part were included. The participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of the information they provide. No financial benefit was offered to participants.

CHAPTER FOUR

4. Results

A total of 110 responders from the Faculty of Medicine at the International University of Africa filled the Questionnaire with a response rate of 100%. They are a mix of Sudanese and non-Sudanese students.

Table (4.1): Distribution of participants according to Age, Gender, Marital Status, Nationality, Reasons for Studying Medicine etc. Faculty of Medicine, I.U.A. Khartoum, Sudan. (n=110)

VARIABLES		FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE			
	18 – 20	0	0%
	20 – 23	47	42.6%
	23 – 26	53	48.5%
	More than 26	10	8.9%
GENDER			
	Male	58	52.9%
	Female	52	47.1%
MARITAL STATUS			
	Single	107	97.1%
	Married	3	2.9%
NATIONALITY			
	Sudanese	21	19.1%
	Other	89	80.9%
REASONS FOR STUDYING MBBS PROGRAM			
	Self-motivation	78	71.5%
	Parents wish	18	16.4%
	Social Status	12	10.5%
	Peer Influence	2	1.6%

MODE OF TRANSPORTATION			
	Bus	16	14.7%
	Own car	5	4.6%
	Public Transport	49	44.1%
	Walking	37	33.8%
	Bike	3	2.8%
TIME TAKEN TO REACH COLLEGE			
	0-15 Minutes	83	75.0%
	15-60 Minutes	24	22.1%
	More than 60 Minutes	3	2.9%
PLACE OF HAVING MEAL			
	College	16	14.7%
	Canteen/Café	7	6.1%
	Restaurant	13	11.6%
	Home	74	67.6%
MEAL TIME COINCIDING WITH LECTURES			
	Yes	52	47.1%
	No	58	52.9%

The demographic results show that none of the students who participated in the research is below the age of twenty. Most of the students are between the ages of 23 to 26, and that is 48.5% of them. The second largest age group comprises of those between the ages of 20 to 23. They form 42.6%. Only 8.9% of the students are above the age of 26.

The participants are 52.9% Male and 47.1% Female, with 97.1% single while a meagre 2.9% are married. A significantly large number of the students who joined the study are non-Sudanese, which could imply that they may have spent years away from home. This research has not delved into the mental and emotional health consequences of missing family and loved ones, a phenomenon which could potentially contribute to student absenteeism.

The vast majority of the participants (71.5%) opted to study Medicine from personal motivation. These students are most likely to be more committed to their studies as opposed to those who chose the field due to the wish of their parents (16.4%) as well as those who chose it on the basis of improved social status (10.5%). As for the students who opted to study Medicine as a result of peer influence, they form the least minority as per the results (1.6%). The level of motivation of these students is probably relative, because it depends on whether the influence they initially had is still relevant to them. Yet, it is conceivable that they may have found other sources of motivation over the years, considering the fact that they are all in their clinical years at the time of participating in this study.

Most of the participants travel to the faculty by means of public transport (44.1%). They are followed in number by those who walk instead (33.8%), those who take the bus (14.7%), those who have a private car (4.6%) and those who use a bike (2.8%). These factors are important because transport cost and length can hinder student attendance. 75% of them spend 0-15 minutes on the way before reaching the faculty. This seems quite reasonable and convenient and it shows that majority of the participants do not live so far away from the faculty. It also shows that there are adequate traffic conditions within a few kilometres of the university. 22.1% of the participants reach the faculty between 15 and 60 minutes while only 2.9% spend more than an hour on the way, probably because they either live far or they are disabled.

Lectures in medical school can be lengthy, often spanning a great deal of morning and afternoon hours. This makes meal times an essential parameter for judging potential motivations behind student absenteeism. 67.6% of the participants take their meal at home. 14.7% at the college. 11.6% at the restaurant. And 6.1% at the canteen/café. 52.9% of them believe that meal time coincides with lectures. These are the students most likely to skip lectures in order to take their meal. On the other hand, 47.1% believe that meal time does not coincide with lectures. This group may have other motivations for skipping lectures but not meal timing. The results here also show similarities in meal timing among members of the first group. And a similar case can be made for the members of the second group.

Figure (4.1): Participants’ responses according to time taken to reach the faculty/college. Medical School, I.U.A. (n=110)

Table (4.2): Participants’ Response on the Reasons for not attending Lectures. Faculty of Medicine, I.U.A. Khartoum, Sudan. (n=110)

Reasons For Not Attending Lectures	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I don't attend lectures as I can take them from my friends.	13, (11.8%)	26, (23.5%)	16, (14.7%)	32, (29.4%)	23, (20.6%)
I feel health related issues have a huge effect on my attendance.	15, (13.2%)	44, (39.7%)	13, (11.8%)	25, (23.5%)	13, (11.8%)
I prefer self/group studying over attending lectures	30, (27.9%)	34, (30.9%)	7, (6.1%)	34, (30.9%)	5, (4.2%)
I feel I can pass exams without attending lectures	28, (25.0%)	42, (38.2%)	11, (10.3%)	24, (22.1%)	5, (4.4%)
Lack of interest in the subject	15, (13.2%)	31, (27.9%)	23, (20.6%)	34, (30.9%)	7, (7.4%)

Poor teaching strategies by lecturers	18, (16.2%)	47, (42.6%)	19, (17.6%)	24, (22.1%)	2, (1.5%)
Desire for attending parties and activities with peers	8, (7.4%)	47, (42.6%)	26, (23.5%)	21, (19.1%)	8, (7.4%)
Negative self-image and low self-esteem	7, (6.0%)	26, (23.9%)	20, (17.9%)	39, (35.8%)	18, (16.4%)
Mental capacity does not match with medical studies	5, (4.9%)	30, (27.5%)	16, (14.7%)	43, (38.2%)	16, (14.7%)
Feeling homesick	7, (5.9%)	40, (36.8%)	21, (19.1%)	34, (30.9%)	8, (7.4%)
Attendance of lectures does not affect the achievement of good grades	13, (11.9%)	38, (34.3%)	18, (16.4%)	31, (28.4%)	10, (9.0%)
Even if I don't attend, the lecture notes from peers are enough.	7, (5.9%)	42, (38.3%)	21, (19.1%)	26, (23.5%)	14, (13.2%)
Do not understand language used by lecturers	13, (11.8%)	29, (26.5%)	14, (13.2%)	31, (27.9%)	23, (20.6%)
Not interested in certain topics	5, (4.6%)	45, (41.2%)	29, (26.5%)	23, (20.6%)	8, (7.1%)
Depend on YouTube to learn medical information	26, (23.5%)	52, (47.1%)	23, (22.1%)	4, (3.8%)	5, (4.5%)
YouTube can take the place of lectures	26, (23.5%)	32, (29.4%)	23, (20.6%)	21, (19.1%)	8, (7.4%)
Depend on medical apps for learning	10, (8.8%)	57, (51.5%)	18, (16.2%)	19, (17.6%)	6, (5.9%)
Apps are useful and sufficient	19, (17.6%)	52, (47.1%)	19, (17.6%)	14, (11.8%)	6, (5.9%)

With regard to the reasons for absenteeism, 23.5% of participants agree that they do not attend lectures when they can easily take them from friends, but 29.4% disagree on this matter. In fact, 20.6% strongly disagree. The rest of the percentage is shared between those who stand neutral (14.7%) and those who strongly agree (11.8%).

Besides these two reasons for absenteeism, the table above details the response of participants on the rest of a range of potential reasons for their skipping of lectures.

Figure (4.2): Participants' Dependence on YouTube. I.U.A. Medical School. (n=110)

The figure above shows that most of the participant heavily depend on YouTube to learn medicine. Notably, 22.5% strongly agree to this dependence while a surging 47.1% agree. That is nearly half of the participants. Only a meagre 4.8% strongly disagree, supported by 3.8% who disagree. This outcome is not surprising considering the dominant role of the internet and modern technology in the lives of the modern generation.

In fact, majority of the participants opine that YouTube can take the place of lectures. Though the difference in opinion here is not as large as in the previous, it is still quite significant. In comparison, it can be deduced that even though a large number of participants depend on YouTube, a significant number of them do not think it can effectively replace lectures.

Figure (4.3): Participants' Dependence on Medical Apps for Knowledge. I.U.A. Medical School. (n=110)

As illustrated above, medical apps are popular amongst students. Out of 110 participants, more than 50 use apps to learn, and more than 50 think as well that these apps are sufficient. In addition, 10 more people strongly agree to the former while 19 more people strongly agree to the latter.

Figure (4.4): Participants' responses on feelings of homesickness. I.U.A. Medical School. (=110)

From the above diagram, it is established that many students suffer from homesickness. Most of the medical students at the International University of Africa are foreigners, and a significant number of them are African. This implies that they may come from low income backgrounds, so the prospect of travelling home to see family at the end of the academic year, for instance, is ruled out.

CHAPTER FIVE

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to find out the dominant causes of medical student absenteeism at the International University of Africa, especially the role of technology such as YouTube and medical apps in that regard.

The results have clearly shown that technology has indeed changed the nature of the educational arena. YouTube is rife with videos of medical practitioners who explain medical information, skills and procedures in detail. Students understandably opt for this choice because it grants them some notable advantages:

- It allows them to learn at their own timing. Given that matters such as transport related issues, health status, meal timing, homesickness etc. affect student attendance as shown in the results of this study, learning through YouTube provides relief to students who suffer these circumstances. And from this, it is evident too that both academic and non-academic workload are potential factors that determine student absenteeism^{28, 29}.
- Besides conventional classroom learning, YouTube grants students the opportunity to agreeably share their views on the contents of the learning materials they use (in his case, videos). The platform rewards content creators financially based on how many views they get, and that is the reason some medical lecturers use the platform as a side income stream. So in order to attract more viewers, they seek feedback from the consumers of their contents in a bid to make improvements. As a result, these videos improve in quality over time because both the content creators and the consumers have a self interest in the achievement of this end. This may be one reason why absenteeism is a growing trend^{25, 26, 27, 35}.

On the other hand, classroom learning is based on a fixed curricula and improvements in both content and modes of delivery do not happen quite quickly. In fact, many students report that lectures are occasionally boring. And even if lecturers and the administration recognize this

issue, there may be no impetus on their side to immediately change the status quo. One can factor such a scenario as a reason why 58.6% of the participants report that poor teaching strategies also affect their motivation and attitude towards attending lectures^{30, 31, 33}.

Also, nearly half of the participants reported that they lack interest in certain topics. Essentially, this means they are not motivated to attend lessons on these topics. Most schools do not have a feedback system to find out and properly address this interest gap. By providing this privilege, YouTube gives students a say in the education they are getting. And that, in itself, is a remarkable social motivating factor.

At the heart of this matter is that conventional lectures do not have a monopoly on the provision of relevant medical information. YouTube videos have increasingly become a convenient alternative method, and this may be the reason why more than half of the participants reported that YouTube can in fact take the place of lectures. Those who sat on the fence with regards to this are also significant, but only a few students rejected this notion. This may also be one of the reasons why many students reported that attendance of lectures does not affect grades³². Nonetheless, the percentage of those who oppose this point is significant. Individual intelligence, hard work and resourcefulness are also conceivable as relevant contributors to this result but this study has not delved into those.

Furthermore, the results show that students also depend heavily on medical apps. Though YouTube is a video platform, these apps can contain text, diagrams and videos.

Apps, just like YouTube are alternative sources of information. 64.7% of the participants have reported that apps are useful and sufficient, which implies that dependence on them is adequate for scoring good grades.

Besides, half of the participants disagree to the opinion that they do not attend lectures because they can get the files from their colleagues afterwards. It is only 35.3% who agree to this opinion with 14.7% sitting on the fence. Just as this outcome can be triggered by many different motivations, it may also be motivated or even heightened by the participants' relative ability to surf the internet for apps and videos containing relevant information.

Interestingly, 44.2% of these students reported that these lecture notes that they get from their peers are enough to perform well academically. They are countered by 36.7% of participants who

reported that this practice is not a sufficient way to score well in exams. The dominant reasoning here is that even though most of the students object to the practice of skipping classes because they can simply get the notes from their colleagues, they still tend to ask their friends for help in case they inadvertently miss lectures, for example, when they travel or when they fall sick.

More students have reported that they prefer self/group studying over attending lectures. This feeling is most likely dependent on how interesting and emotionally enticing conventional lectures are in relation to self/group studies. Probably, participants do not find much emotional appeal in lectures, thus preferring discussions with peers. This form of learning too is encouraged in curricula across the world, because people tend to learn faster from their colleagues in informal situations than from their lecturers in formal classroom settings. Such desire may be the reason why many students reported that teaching strategies ought to be improved, even though a striking majority of them report they actually understand the language used by the lecturers.

With regards to whether medical school is hard and that the courses offered overwhelm their mental capacity, most participants' reported in the negative. This implies their strong belief in their ability to handle the undergraduate medical training they are receiving, and it also implies that any failures can be attributed instead to other factors. And more than half of them reported that negative self-image and low self-esteem are not a problem for them at all. Meanwhile, 29.9% reported that they suffer from these issues. So long mental health status is crucial for an effective and functional life, this percentage could be a significant determinant of the scourge of absenteeism, which is reported to be an important factor in reduced academic performance³⁴.

In conclusion, the results obtained from this study confirm the drastic effect of technological advancement on traditional educational systems. Apparently, technology has infiltrated every facet of society. This development may not be inherently negative, but the possibility of abuse is quite high.

YouTube and medical apps have become principal learning tools for many students, even if they rely, to some degree, on lectures as well. And the fact that many students have reported that these systems are actually sufficient for them reflects their degree of reliance on these sites, as it also reflects the degree of the effectiveness of these sites in delivering essential medical knowledge to users.

Conclusion

It is fair to state that there are many factors that lead to medical student absenteeism. Yet in the context of this study, the following inferences have been made.

- Medical student absenteeism is not a major concern among the students themselves.
- Many students believe they can do without attending lectures by depending on alternative sources of learning.
- Students believe that YouTube and medical apps can provide them significant medical information sufficient for scoring well in exams.
- Teaching methods and techniques are important motivations for improved lecture attendances.
- Emotional stresses such as homesickness affects the lecture attendance level of international students.

CHAPTER SIX

6. Recommendations and Limitations

Recommendations

The recommendations we have deduced from the results of this study are in three categories:

- Students
- Staff
- Administration

Meanwhile, generally, we would stress the need for medical students and faculty members to be aware of the short and long term consequences of absenteeism to students, medical schools and the society at large.

Students

- a) So long absenteeism has been identified as an obstacle to good academic performance, students should consider attending lectures to boost their grades.
- b) Students should negotiate with the administration to request the provision of needed facilities that would guarantee increased lecture attendances.
- c) Students should report to the administration and the staff what they consider to be existing structural and academic obstacles toward achieving a drastically improved net attendance level.

Staff

- a) The staff should device means of making the learning process interactive, lively and interesting.
- b) The staff should further digitalize the learning tools such that they are at par with modern technological standards.

- c) Staff should seek constructive feedback from students with regards to the arrangement of the curricula as well as lecturer presentation deficits.

Administration

- a) The administration should provide constant and reliable internet connection within the faculty premises to entice students to be present for lectures always.
- b) Training programs should be provided to the teaching staff to improve their teaching methodology and to alter their orientation from the traditional lecturing methods to more interactive methods.
- c) An office should be established to professionally address the personal problems of students that keep them from attending lectures.

Limitations

The study has certain limitations that can be taken into consideration in future studies. The study's sample size was limited and results could have been more objective oriented with larger samples by incorporating the medical student population of other universities. Random sampling was used which did not dig into the specifics of medical student absenteeism, and it bears the propensity for some inherent bias.

References

1. Randa, M.B., 2020. An Exploration of Absenteeism among Nursing Students in the context of a South African University. *The Open Nursing Journal*, 14(1).
2. Fayombo, G.A., Ogunkola, B.J. and Olaleye, Y.L., 2012. Cross institutional study of the causes of absenteeism among university students in Barbados and Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Developmental Psychology*, 2(1), p.122.
3. Nawaz, K., Hussain, M., Sarwar, H., Afzal, M. and Gilani, S.A., 2018. Determine the factors influencing absenteeism among nursing students. *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing*, 50(7), pp.64-72.
4. Auerbach, R.P., Mortier, P., Bruffaerts, R., Alonso, J., Benjet, C., Cuijpers, P., Demyttenaere, K., Ebert, D.D., Green, J.G., Hasking, P. and Murray, E., 2018. WHO World Mental Health Surveys International College Student Project: Prevalence and distribution of mental disorders. *Journal of abnormal psychology*, 127(7), p.623.
5. Ntho, T.A., 2020. Reinforcement of an under-graduate peer-group clinical mentoring programme in nursing (Doctoral dissertation, North-West University (South-Africa)).
6. Nagda, B.A., Gregerman, S.R., Jonides, J., Von Hippel, W. and Lerner, J.S., 1998. Undergraduate student-faculty research partnerships affect student retention. *The Review of Higher Education*, 22(1), pp.55-72.
7. Magobolo, G.N. and Dube, B.M., 2019. Factors influencing high absenteeism rate of student nurses in clinical areas at a nursing college in the Lejweleputswa District. *Curationis*, 42(1), pp.1-6.
8. Gelo, A., Damena, M., Geleto, A. and Kenay, A., 2021. Prevalence of school absenteeism during menstruation and associated factors in sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic review and meta-analysis protocol.
9. Van Wyk, G. and Hodgkinson-Williams, C.A., Staff insights on opening up learning to students with disabilities at Motheo TVET College, South Africa. *Open Learning as a Means of Advancing Social Justice*, p.178.
10. Scheckle, L., 2014. An Activity Theory analysis: reasons for undergraduate students' absenteeism at a South African university. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 28(2), pp.605-623.

11. Sharmin T, Azim E, Choudbury S and Kamrun S (2017): Reasons of Absenteeism among Undergraduate Medical Students: A Review. *Answer Khan Modern Medical College Journal*, 8(1): 60-6.
12. Wadesango N and Machingambi S (2011): Causes and structural effects of student absenteeism: a case study of three South African Universities. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 26(2): 89-97.
13. Merghani T, Haroun B and Elmubarak I (2013): Self-report of voluntary absenteeism from didactic lectures by medical students. *Universal Journal of Education and General Studies*, 213(10):324-8.
14. Desalegn A, Berhan, A and Berhan Y (2014): Absenteeism among medical and health science undergraduate students at Hawassa University, Ethiopia. *BMC medical education*, 14(1): 81.
15. Kottasz R (2005): Reasons for student non-attendance at lectures and tutorials: an analysis. *Investigations in university teaching and learning*, 2(2):5-16.
16. BinSaeed A, Al-Otaibi M, Al-Ziyadi H, Babsail A and Shaik S (2009): Association between student absenteeism at a medical college and their academic grades. *The Journal of the International Association of Medical Science Educators*, 19(4): 155-159
17. Miiro, G., Rutakumwa, R., Nakiyingi-Miiro, J., Nakuya, K., Musoke, S., Namakula, J., Francis, S., Torondel, B., Gibson, L.J., Ross, D.A. and Weiss, H.A., 2018. Menstrual health and school absenteeism among adolescent girls in Uganda (MENISCUS): a feasibility study. *BMC women's health*, 18(1), pp.1-13.
18. Qutub, M.F., Azahrani, A.A., Bafail, M.A., Alomari, A.S., Abuznadah, W.T., Alsaywid, B.S.A., Munshi, F.M. and Alsaywid, B.S., 2018. Absenteeism among Saudi medical students. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*, 70(8), pp.1248-1253.
19. Longhurst, R. J. (1999) Why aren't They Here? Student Absenteeism in a Further Education College, *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 23, 1, pp.61-80.
20. Ford, J., Bosworth D. and Wilson, R. (1995) Part Time Work and Full Time Higher Education, *Studies in Higher Education*, 20, 2, pp. 187-202.
21. Fleming, N. (1992) Why Don't They Attend? Occasional Paper, Education Unit, Lincoln University.
22. Hidi, S. (1990) Interest and its Contribution as a Mental Resource for Learning, *Review of Educational Research*, 60, pp. 549-571.

23. Entwistle, N. (1998) *Motivation and Approaches to Learning* in Brown, S., Armstrong, S. and Thompson, G. (1998) (Eds.) *Motivating Students*, Kogan Page, London.
24. Bennett, R. (2001) *Lecturers' Attitudes towards New Teaching Methods*, *International Journal of Management Education*, 2, 1, pp. 42-56.
25. Massingham P, Herrington T: Does attendance matter? An examination of student attitudes, participation, performance and attendance. *J Univ Teach Learn Prac* 2006, 3(3):207—2012
26. Dolnicar S, Kaiser S, Matus K, Viallem W: Can Australian Universities measure to increase the lecture attendance of marketing students? *J Mark Edu* 2009, 31(3)203—211.
27. Moorea S, Armstronga C, Pearsona J: Lecture absenteeism among students in higher education: a valuable route to understanding motivation. *J High Educ Policy Manag* 200, 30(1):15—24.
28. Devadoss S, Foltz J: Evaluation of factors influencing students' class attendance and performance. *Am J Agr Econ* 1996, 78(3):499—509.
29. Wadesango N, Machingambi S: Causes and structural effects of student absenteeism: a case study of three South African Universities. *J Soc Sci* 2011, 26(2):89—97.
30. Paisey C, Paisey NJ: Student attendance in an accounting module – reasons for non-attendance and the effect on academic performance at a Scottish University. *Acc Educ* 2004, 13(1):39—52.
31. Gump SE: Guess who's (not) coming to class: student attitudes as indicators of attendance. *Educ Stud* 2006, 32(1):39—46.
32. Rao BT, Valleswary K, Durga MS, Nayak P and Rao NL. (2016) Reasons for absenteeism among undergraduate medical students attending for theory classes in Rajiv Handhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS) Ongole, Prakasam District of Andhra Pradesh: A Self Review. *Journal of Research and Method in Education*. 6(4):11—9.
33. Desalegn AA, Berhan A and Berha Y. (2014) Absenteeism among medical and health science undergraduate students at Hawassa University, Ethiopia, *BMC Medical Education* 14:14—81.
34. Gul R, Khan HM, Alam SR, Luqman F, Shahab A, Sohail H. Absenteeism among medical undergraduate students. *J med sci*. 2016; 24(1):16–8.
35. Sial NA, Humayun R, Humayun F. Evaluation of factors causing absenteeism from lectures in a medical college. *Khyber Med Univ J* 2018; 10(3):135-9.

ANNEXES

Annex 1:

The Questionnaire

Part 1: Personal Data

1. Age:

- A. 18–20
- B. 20–23
- C. 23–26
- D. >26

2. Gender

- A. Male
- B. Female

3. Marital Status

- A. Single
- B. Married

4. Nationality

- A. Sudanese
- B. Other

5. Reason for studying MBBS Program

- A. Self-Motivation
- B. Parents' Wish
- C. Social Status

D. Peer Influence

6. Mode of Transport used to Commute College

A. Bus

B. Own Car

C. Public transport

D. Walking

E. Bike

7. Time taken to reach college

A. 0 -15 minutes

B. 15 - 60 minutes

C. > 60 minutes

8. Place of having meal

A. College

B. Canteen/Cafe

C. Restaurant

D. Home

9. Meal time coincides with lectures

A. Yes

B. No

Part 3:

Reasons For Not Attending Lectures	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I don't attend lectures as I can take them from my friends.					
I feel health related issues have a huge effect on my attendance.					
I prefer self/group studying over attending lectures					
I feel that I can pass exams without attending lectures.					
Lack of interest in the subject					
Poor teaching strategies by lecturers					
desire for attending parties and activities with peers					
Negative self-image and low self-esteem					
Mental capacity does not match with medical studies					
Feeling homesick					
Attendance of lectures does not affect the achievement of good grades					
Even if I don't attend, the lecture notes from peers are enough.					
Do not understand language used by lecturers					
Not interested in certain topics					
Depend on YouTube to learn medical information					
YouTube can take the place of lectures					
Depend on medical apps for learning					
Apps are useful and sufficient					

Annex 2:

Budget Estimation

Item	Price
Proposal Printing	700 SDG
Internet Fees for the Questionnaire	5000 SDG
Data Analysis	1000 SDG
Final Thesis Printing	10000 SDG
Other	5000 SDG
Total	21,700 SDG

Annex 3:

Timetable

Time	2022			
	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov
Activities				
Proposal Preparation				
Data Collection				
Analysis				
Report Writing and Presenting for Discussion				

Annex 4:

Figure (7.1) Geographical Map of Sudan

Figure (7.2) Geographical Map of I.U.A

